

Chimú Empire Religion

By Amedeo Sghinolfi, Western University

Entry tags: Prehistoric South American Religions, Andes, Peru, Quignam, Religious Group, Latin America Religions, Language, Unclassifiable, South American Religions

The Chimú empire developed on the North Coast of Peru between ca. 900 and 1470 CE and its peak it was one of the largest Prehispanic polities in the Americas. The 1604 Anonymous History of Trujillo includes a mythical account of Chimú origins (Rowe 1948). A foreign noble called Taycanamo arrived in the Moche Valley, disembarking from a balsa log raft, claiming to be sent by a great lord from across the sea. He spent a year to learn local customs and traditions. He was given local women for wives and became Chimú ruler (Chimor Capac), establishing a dynasty. Chan Chan, the capital of the empire, was located in the Moche Valley and it was the largest urban center of its time, covering about 20km² (urban core 6 km²) and hosting 30,000-40,000 people. In an alternative origin myth recorded by Percy Valladares Huamanchumo (2021), the city may have been founded by a man who was born from an egg laid by the Moon in the Guañape islands. The man was raised by people living in the fishing village of Huanchaco. Eventually, he became their leader and founded Chan Chan. Chan Chan featured a variety of buildings made with sunbaked adobe bricks or tapia (rammed earth) walls, including walled royal compounds (ciudadelas), elite compounds, ceremonial platforms (huacas), and residential areas for commoners/artisans. As shown by these architectural compounds and by creation myths, people were subdivided into well-defined, and perhaps immutable, social classes. A myth mentioned by Antonio de la Calancha says that coastal people were created by four stars: two stars created kings and nobles, while the other two stars created commoners. Another myth recorded by the same author described the creation of social classes from three eggs. Royal and noble males spawned from a golden egg, noble women from a silver egg, and commoners from a copper egg (Calancha 1638; Mackey and Moore 2008; Moseley and Cordy-Collins 1990; Rowe 1948). By 1200 CE, the Chimú empire consolidated its power in its heartland, which was composed of the Moche, Chicama, and Virú valleys. The 14th century was marked by a significant expansion of the empire: in that century, the Chimú expanded northward, conquering the lands controlled by the Lambayeque/Sicán polity (the area comprised between the Lambayeque and the Chira valleys), and southward, defeating the Casma polity and occupying its territory (between Chao and Casma valleys). The empire may have also exerted its influence further north to Tumbes and south to the Chillón valley through trade. At its peak, the Chimú empire featured a four-tiered settlement hierarchy, with the capital Chan Chan at the top, followed by the regional centers of Farfán, Túcume, and Manchan, and tertiary and quaternary centers scattered throughout the empire. The Chimú dominance over the North Coast of Peru came to an end around 1470 CE, when the Inka defeated them and incorporated this part of the Central Andes into their empire. Excavations carried out at Chimú settlements and ethnohistorical sources help us shed light on the religious practices of the people that occupied the North Coast of Peru during the Late Intermediate Period (ca. 900/1000-1470 CE).

Date Range: 900 CE - 1470 CE

Region: Chimú Empire

Region tags: Andes, Peru

The Chimú Empire at its peak (ca. 1470)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though it is not clear, the co-rule of some Chimu' provincial centers (see Manchán and Túcume) might indicate that local cults survived

Reference: Mackey, Carol . "Chimu Statecraft in the Provinces". In *Andean Civilization: A Tribute to Michael E. Moseley*, edited by Joyce Marcus and Patrick Ryan Williams, 325–50. Los Angeles, CA: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology , 2009.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: See conquest of the Lambayeque/Sicán polity (Aimi, Makowski and Perassi 2017; Shimada 1995; Wester 2021) to the north and the Casma polity (Vogel 2012; 2016) to the south (Moore and Mackey 2008). See also signs of conflict from human remains found at Pacatnamu' (territory of the Lambayeque/Sican polity) and at Punta Lobos (Huarney Valley) (Verano 1986, 2008).

Reference: Wester, Carlos, ed.. *Naimlap: Memoria Lambayeque Y Materialidad Histórica*. Edited by Carlos Wester. Lima, Peru: Apus Graph Ediciones, 2021.

Reference: Aimi, Antonio, Krzysztof Makowski, and Emilia Perassi, eds.. *Lambayeque: Nuevos Horizontes De La Arqueología Peruana*. Edited by Antonio Aimi, Krzysztof Makowski, and Emilia Perassi. Milano, Italy: Ledizioni, 2017.

Reference: Shimada, Izumi. *Cultura Sican: Dios, Riqueza Y Poder En La Costa Norte Del Peru*. Lima, Peru: Edubanco, 1995.

Reference: Vogel, Melissa A.. *Frontier Life in Ancient Peru: The Archaeology of Cerro La Cruz*. Gainesville, FL: University Press of Florida, 2012.

Reference: Vogel, Melissa A.. *The Casma City of El Purgatorio Ancient Urbanism in the Andes*. Gainesville, FL: University Press of Florida, 2016.

Reference: Verano, John W.. "A Mass Burial of Mutilated Individuals at Pacatnamu". In *Pacatnamu Papers*, edited by Christopher B. Donnan and Guillermo A. Cock, Vol. 1. Los Angeles, CA: Fowler Museum of Culture History, University of California, 1986.

Reference: Verano, John W.. "Trophy Head-taking and Human Sacrifice in Andean South America". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York, NY: Springer, 2008.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The most significant conflict took place around 1460-1470 CE, when the Chimú and the Inka empires fought for the control of the north coast of Peru. The conflict ended with conquest of this part of the Andes by the Inka troops led by Pachakuti's son and future emperor Thupa Inka Yupanqui. As mentioned by John Rowe (1948), during this conflict the Chimú may have been allied with the Cajamarca people (Peruvian Northern Highlands). It must be noted that recent research highlights that the Inka expansion may have taken place earlier than argued in the texts written by the chroniclers (see Covey 2020, p. 53; Marsh et al. 2017; Ogburn 2012).

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: D'Altroy, Terence N.. *The Incas*. 2nd ed.. Wiley Blackwell, 2014.

Reference: Covey, Alan R.. *Inca Apocalypse: The Spanish Conquest and the Transformation of the Andean World*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2020.

Reference: Quilter, Jeffrey. *The Ancient Central Andes*. 2nd ed.. Routledge, 2022.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Marsh, Erik J., Ray Kidd, Dennis Ogburn, and Víctor Durán. "Dating the Expansion of the Inca Empire: Bayesian Models from Ecuador and Argentina". *Radiocarbon* 59, no. 1 (2017): 117–40. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2016.118>.

Reference: Ogburn, Dennis E. "Reconceiving the Chronology of Inca Imperial Expansion". *Radiocarbon* 54, no. 2 (2012): 219–37. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2458/azu_js_rc.v54i2.16014.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Priests may have lived in royal/elite compounds at centers like Chan Chan, Farfan or Manchan. These compounds included several storage rooms, which may have stored, among other things, foods to sustain the members of the royal family, nobles and perhaps priestly figures. John Rowe (1948: 49) argues that curers were public officials and that they were paid a wage by the empire.

Reference: Moseley, Michael E., and Kent C. Day, eds.. *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*. Edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The construction of ceremonial buildings such as plazas and platforms (huacas) was likely directed by royalty/state administrators. Large swaths of the population likely participated in the construction and this manpower was probably mobilized through a labor tax system resembling the Inka mit'a (Moseley 1975).

Reference: Moseley, Michael E.. "Prehistoric Principles of Labor Organization in the Moche Valley, Peru". *American Antiquity* 40, no. 2 (1975): 191-96. <https://doi.org/10.2307/279614>.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though it is not clear, it is a possibility (see also the role of the Sapa Inka in the coeval Inka society - D'Altroy 2014). Some scholars (Conrad 1982; Uceda 1999) argue that Chimú rulers may have had a divine nature. In addition, a Chimú origin myth further suggests a possible divine nature of the ruling class. As argued by Valladares Huamanchumo (2020, p. 49), the mythical founder of Chan Chan was the son of the moon.

Reference: D'Altroy, Terence N.. *The Incas*. 2nd ed.. Wiley Blackwell, 2014.

Reference: Valladares Huamanchumo, Percy. *Historias Del Abuelo*. Lima, Peru: Ediciones Rafael Valdez E. I. R. L., 2021.

Reference: Conrad, Geoffrey W.. "The Burial Platforms of Chan Chan: Some Social and Political Implications". In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day , 87-118. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Culto a Los Muertos Y a Los Ancestros: Escenas in Miniatura Y Una Maqueta En La Epoca Chimú". *Arkinka* 49 (1999): 72-83.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though it is not clear, Early Colonial ethnohistorical sources from the North Coast of Peru highlights that local leaders also had a ritual presence.

Reference: Netherly, Patricia J.. "The Management of Late Andean Irrigation Systems on the North Coast of Peru". *American Antiquity* 49, no. 2 (1984). <https://doi.org/10.2307/280017>.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:
– Yes

Notes: John Rowe (1948) argues that punishments for robbery had both a civil and a religious nature since private property was considered a divine right.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:
– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we do not know how people lived in the whole empire and adhered to this religion. However, it has been estimated that between 30,000 and 40,000 people lived in the capital of the empire, Chan Chan.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know what percentage of people adhered to the official imperial cult. It is possible that in different parts of the empire people preserved local cults (Ravines 1980, p. 215).

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The emperor likely had both a political and a religious role within society, especially if he was considered a descendant of the son of the moon (Valladares Huamanchumo, pp. 47-49)

Reference: Valladares Huamanchumo, Percy. *Historias Del Abuelo*. Lima, Peru: Ediciones Rafael Valdez E. I. R. L., 2021.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely yes, but it is not certain

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Following the traditions of their predecessors (see, for example, Cupisnique and Moche), leaders and priests were likely considered able to connect with supernatural beings, especially if they were somewhat related to them.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Valladares Huamanchumo, Percy. *Historias Del Abuelo*. Lima, Peru: Ediciones Rafael Valdez E. I. R. L., 2021.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative

and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Chimú sites, and especially the capital and the provincial administrative centers, feature several buildings that had a ceremonial purpose (e.g., ceremonial platforms/huacas, funerary platforms, plazas, and perhaps U-shaped structures called audiencias).

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. “The Chimú Empire”. In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Ravines, Rogger, ed.. *Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú*. Edited by Rogger Ravines. Lima: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

Reference: Moseley, Michael E., and Kent C. Day, eds.. *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*. Edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Reference: Mullins, Patrick J.. *Legacies in the Landscape: Borderland Processes in the Upper Moche Valley Chaupiyunga of Peru*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh, 2022.

In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 100

Notes: This is the size of Huaca Toledo in Chan Chan, excavated in the 2010s (Meneses Bartra 2020). It should be noted that Kent C. Day (1982) argues that Huaca El Obispo is larger than Huaca Toledo, but the Huaca El Obispo has never been excavated so we do not know its actual size.

Reference: Meneses Bartra, Jorge. “El Mundo Ceremonial De Chan Chan: Investigaciones En Huaca Toledo”. In *Chan Chan: Esplendor Y Legado*, edited by Carlos Rengifo, 93-134. Colección Cultura, Investigación E Historia. Lima, Peru: Ministerio de Cultura del Peru, 2020.

Reference: Day, Kent C.. “Ciudadelas: Their Form and Function”. In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 55-65. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 22

Notes: 22 meters is the height of Huaca Toledo in Chan Chan, which has been excavated in the 2010s (Meneses Bartra 2020). It should be noted that, according to Kent C. Day (1982), Huaca El Obispo in Chan Chan is larger than Huaca Toledo. Huaca El Obispo has not been excavated yet and we do not know its exact height.

Reference: Meneses Bartra, Jorge. "El Mundo Ceremonial De Chan Chan: Investigaciones En Huaca Toledo". In Chan Chan: Esplendor Y Legado, edited by Carlos Rengifo, 93-134. Colección Cultura, Investigación E Historia. Lima, Peru: Ministerio de Cultura del Peru, 2020.

Reference: Day, Kent C.. "Ciudadelas: Their Form and Function". In Chan Chan: Andean Desert City, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 55-65. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Within the royal compounds (ciudadelas) identified at the capital of the empire, Chan Chan in the Moche Valley, are nine burial platforms. These platforms are elevated structures that could be accessed through a system of ramps and featured cells with deceased individuals and grave goods (see Conrad 1982, p. 88-89, figure 5.1). These platforms were built using adobe bricks or with tapiales (rammed-earth technique) and they included a principal T-shaped cell in the center of the platform surrounded by secondary cells in various shapes (simple and boot shaped shafts). The number of funerary cells ranged from about 15 (ciudadela Fochic An - ex Squier) to 100 (ciudadela Utzh An - ex Gran Chimu'). In front of the platform was an enclosed court. Excavations conducted in the platforms yielded human remains and prestige goods (decorated pottery, textiles, metal and wooden objects, Spondylus shells etc.): however, looting heavily affected the intactness of these tombs. The platforms likely served as mortuary structures for high-status individuals living in Chan Chan. The principal individual was buried in the central cell/chamber, and this event was followed by human and animal (llama) sacrifices and by the deposition of grave goods. Sacrificed individuals and perhaps attendants/relatives/high-level administrators were interred in secondary cells. These rituals were repeated over time and architectural additions including other funerary cells. Even though it is not certain, the principal individuals interred in these platforms may have been Chimu' rulers. As suggested by Pillsbury (2008) and by a wooden object found by Santiago

Uceda (2008) at Huacas de Moche in the Moche Valley, the mummified bodies of high-status individuals may have been periodically pulled out of their chamber and were integral part of ceremonies. However, these ceremonies may have involved only a small part of the population (i.e., elites). Similar platforms have also been found at the provincial sites of Túcume, in the La Leche Valley and Farfán in the Jequetepeque Valley, suggesting that members of Chimú royalty were buried at this provincial sites (Conrad 1990; Mackey 2009).

Reference: Conrad, Geoffrey W.. "The Burial Platforms of Chan Chan: Some Social and Political Implications". In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 87-118. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. "Los Palacios De Chimor". In *Señores De Los Reinos De La Luna*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski. *Arte Y Tesoros Del Peru*. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito - BCP, 2008.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Rituales Funerarios De Los Reyes En Una Maqueta Chimú". In *Señores De Los Reinos De La Luna*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito - BCP, 2008.

Reference: Conrad, Geoffrey W.. "Farfan, General Pacatnamu, and the Dynastic History of Chimor". In *The Northern Dynasties: Kingship and Statecraft in Chimor*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Alana Cordy-Collins, 227-42. Washington, D.C.: *Dumbarton Oaks Research Library and Collection*, 1990.

Reference: Mackey, Carol. "Chimu Statecraft in the Provinces". In *Andean Civilization: A Tribute to Michael E. Moseley*, edited by Joyce Marcus and Patrick Ryan Williams, 325-50. Los Angeles, CA: *Cotsen Institute of Archaeology*, 2009.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. "The Social Basis of Sacred Spaces in the Prehispanic Andes: Ritual Landscapes of the Dead in Chimú and Inka Societies". *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 11, no. 1 (2004): 83-124.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: Architecture and portable objects (e.g., pots, metal objects, textiles)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Possible supernatural figures showing animal traits were depicted at Huaca El Dragon or Huaca Arco Iris, located at the N-E edge of Chan Chan. This building is a two-stage platform with a ramp enclosed by a wall. Friezes on the walls of this building feature a repetition of motifs, including vertical panels depicting several snake/dragon-like figures. Two of these figures face each other, while above them is a two-headed rainbow-shaped figure whose fangs are biting the head of anthropomorphic figures. It has been argued that these figures may have been linked to water and fertility. Similar friezes have been found at Huaca Chotuna in the Lambayeque Valley. Moseley and Kolata (1990) hypothesized that these friezes may also be related to the Naymlap dynasty (the mythical founder of the Lambayeque/Sican people) and this motif may have been brought to Chan Chan (and thus to Huaca El Dragon) to symbolize the Chimu' capture of the main Lambayeque/Sican shrines. However, Donnan (2012) argues that both Huaca Chotuna and Huaca El Dragon may date to a period that precedes the Chimu' conquest of the Lambayeque/Sican, and this motif may have spread from south to north. Another feline/dragon-like figure that appears on Chimu iconography is the Moon Animal, which was also depicted by earlier groups like the Recuay, the Viru', and the Moche. This figure, which may have also been connected to water, is mainly depicted on Chimu' pottery, but is also appears on friezes, like at Huaca El Higo and Huaca Esmeralda (Pillsbury 1993).

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. *Sculpted Friezes of the Empire of Chimor*. New York, NY: Columbia University, 1993.

Reference: Schaedel, Richard P.. "The Huaca El Dragón". *Journal De La Société Des Américanistes* 55, no. 2 (1966): 383–496.

Reference: Bruhns, Karen. "The Moon Animal in Northern Peruvian Art and Culture".

Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies 14, no. 1 (1976): 21-39.
<https://doi.org/10.1179/naw.1976.14.1.002>.

Reference: Donnan, Christopher B.. Chotuna and Chornancap: Excavating an Ancient Peruvian Legend. Monographs 70. Los Angeles, CA: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology Press, 2012.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: The Staff God, a standing, front facing deity, holding staffs in both hands, is depicted on a variety of media (pots, metal objects, textiles, clay friezes). This possible male figure wears a half-moon shaped headdress, a necklace, earspools, as mentioned above, two staffs, and, in some cases, with a sacrificial knife (tumi). Its omnipresence reveals its importance. Staff Gods were depicted also by earlier groups, like Cupisnique, Chavin, and Moche, but in Chimú iconography this figure does not have animal traits. The Plumed Headdress Deity may represent a facet of the Staff God more concerned with human sacrifice. This deity is frequently depicted holding a tumi knife in one hand and a decapitated head in the other. This deity is mainly depicted on pots. The Chimú Goddess is always depicted in three dimensions on ceramics. This deity also wears a headdress, which is either squared or two counterposed tips. This deity was likely related to the sea and the moon.

Reference: Mackey, Carol J.. "Los Dioses Que Perdieron Los Colmillos". In *Los Dioses Del Antiguo Perú*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski, Vol. 2. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito del Perú, 2002.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The wooden model of a ceremonial space and ritual involving a mummified individual found at Huacas de Moche by Santiago Uceda shows the importance played by ancestors in Chimú religion. The wooden model depicts a temple-like structure and a small plaza (decorated with fish-like motifs) that hosts a mummified individual and priestly figures carrying out rituals.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Rituales Funerarios De Los Reyes En Una Maqueta Chimú". In *Señores De Los Reinos De La Luna*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito - BCP, 2008.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Culto a Los Muertos Y a Los Ancestros: Escenas in Miniatura Y Una Maqueta En La Epoca Chimu". *Arkinka* 49 (1999): 72–83.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Human figures are depicted on various friezes and wooden objects located in Chan Chan and in other valleys, such as the Lambayeque Valley. Humans are depicted while they carry out a variety of actions, such as while standing and bearing weapons, diving into the ocean to collect *Spondylus* shells (considered food of the gods by several Andean groups), during funerary processions, as prisoners, sacrificers, and as bearers of offerings.

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. *Sculpted Friezes of the Empire of Chimor*. New York, NY: Columbia University, 1993.

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. "The Thorny Oyster and the Origins of Empire: Implications of Recently Uncovered *Spondylus* Imagery from Chan Chan, Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 7, no. 4 (1996): 313–40. <https://doi.org/10.2307/972262>.

Reference: Donnan, Christopher B.. *Chotuna and Chornancap: Excavating an Ancient Peruvian Legend*. Monographs 70. Los Angeles, CA: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology Press, 2012.

Reference: Jackson, Margaret A.. "The Chimú Sculptures of Huacas Tacaynamo and El Dragon, Moche Valley, Perú". *Latin American Antiquity* 15, no. 3 (2004): 298–322. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4141576>.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Other than religious themes, pots (usually blackwares, produced using molds and fired in an oxidizing atmosphere), textiles, and metal objects feature a variety of motifs, including animals, sea creatures, fruits, vegetables, geometric motifs, and human figures. However, Chimu' iconography rarely features the vividly painted narrative themes that marked Moche art. These type of motifs appeared also on buildings located at key centers like the capital Chan Chan and some of these motifs may have had a religious meaning. As argued by Pillsbury, these buildings usually feature a repetition of the same motif/s may recall the decorations found on textiles.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. "Reading Art Without Writing: Interpreting Chimú Architectural Sculpture". In *Dialogues in Art History, from Mesopotamian to Modern: Readings for a New Century*, edited by Elizabeth Cropper, 73–90. *Studies in the History of Art* 74. New Haven, CT: Center for Advance Study in the Visual Arts - National Gallery

of Art, 2009.

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. *Sculpted Friezes of the Empire of Chimor*. New York, NY: Columbia University, 1993.

Reference: Fleitman, Yvonne, and Alisa Baginski. *Chimu: Imperial Riches from the Desert of Peru*. Jerusalem: The Israel Museum, 2018.

Reference: Pollard Rowe, Ann. "Textiles from the Burial Platform of Las Avispas at Chan Chan". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies* 18, no. 1 (1980): 81-148. <https://doi.org/10.1179/naw.1980.18.1.006>.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Chan Chan with its royal tombs and its position next to the sea had a key political and religious role.

Reference: Ravines, Rogger, ed.. *Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú*. Edited by Rogger Ravines. Lima: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

Reference: Moseley, Michael E., and Kent C. Day, eds.. *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*. Edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: Sakai, Masato. *Reyes, Estrellas Y Cerros En Chimor. El Proceso De Cambio De La Organización Espacial Y Temporal En Chan Chan*. Lima, Peru: Editorial Horizonte, 1998.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: As in other Andean cultures, some landscape features likely had a sacred nature. Sakai (1998) argues that some buildings in Chan Chan may have been built in relation to stars (Pleiades, Sirius, Scorpius constellation, Southern Cross, Piscis Austrinus constellation, and Canis Major constellation) and to stars and mountains (Cerro Blanco and Cerro Prieto) located in the Moche Valley.

Reference: Sakai, Masato. *Reyes, Estrellas Y Cerros En Chimor. El Proceso De Cambio De La Organización Espacial Y Temporal En Chan Chan*. Lima, Peru: Editorial Horizonte, 1998.

Reference: Bray, Tamara L., ed.. *The Archaeology of Wak'as: Explorations of the Sacred in the Pre-columbian Andes*. Edited by Tamara L. Bray. University Press of Colorado, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.5876/9781607323181>.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The discovery of Chimu' architectural model at Huacas de Moche in which mummified individuals are depicted suggests that death may have only marked the end of one of various life stages

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. “Rituales Funerarios De Los Reyes En Una Maqueta Chimú”. In *Señores De Los Reinos De La Luna*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito - BCP, 2008.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. “Culto a Los Muertos Y a Los Ancestros: Escenas in Miniatura Y Una Maqueta En La Epoca Chimu”. *Arkinka* 49 (1999): 72-83.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. “The Social Basis of Sacred Spaces in the Prehispanic Andes: Ritual Landscapes of the Dead in Chimú and Inka Societies”. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 11, no. 1 (2004): 83-124.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Cremation:

– No

Mummification:

– Yes

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Rituales Funerarios De Los Reyes En Una Maqueta Chimú". In *Señores De Los Reinos De La Luna*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito - BCP, 2008.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Culto a Los Muertos Y a Los Ancestros: Escenas in Miniatura Y Una Maqueta En La Epoca Chimu". *Arkinka* 49 (1999): 72-83.

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: People were usually placed in pits circular pits (however, Chan Chan burial platforms feature T-shaped, L-shaped, boot-shaped, and simple shafts). The bodies were placed in different types of positions (extended on their back, extended on one side, flexed).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

Reference: Valladares, Katya. *Social Identities in Chimu Times: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Chayhuac Walled Complex in Chan Chan Site, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2017.

Reference: Donnan, Christopher B., and Carol J. Mackey. *Ancient Burial Patterns of the Moche Valley, Peru*. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 1978.

Reference: Castillo Luján, Feren. "El Chimú Temprano De Huaca De La Luna". In *Actas De La Primera Mesa Redonda De Trujillo. Nuevas Perspectivas En La Arqueología De Los Valles De Virú, Moche Y Chicama*, 232-69. Trujillo, Peru: Fondo Editorial Universitario. Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2019.

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: In some cases, individuals were wrapped in textiles before being placed in pits

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: It should also be noted that in addition to co-sacrifices (i.e., sacrifices of individuals/animals accompanying high status individuals) Chimú people also carried out human sacrifices (see Practices section)

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifices may have been carried out at the royal burial platforms in Chan Chan. However, these contexts have been heavily looted.

Reference: Conrad, Geoffrey W.. "The Burial Platforms of Chan Chan: Some Social and Political Implications". In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 87-118. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Reference: Valladares, Katya. *Social Identities in Chimú Times: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Chayhuac Walled Complex in Chan Chan Site, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2017.

Reference: Ravines, Rogger, ed.. Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú. Edited by Rogger Ravines. Lima: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Llamas

Reference: Conrad, Geoffrey W.. "The Burial Platforms of Chan Chan: Some Social and Political Implications". In Chan Chan: Andean Desert City, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day , 87-118. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Pots, metal objects (copper, silver, gold), shells (*Spondylus*), beads, textiles (plain and decorated), and wooden objects were found in Chimú burials. As mentioned by Donnan and Mackey (1978), metal objects were sometimes placed in the mouth and hands of the deceased.

Reference: Valladares, Katya. *Social Identities in Chimú Times: A Bioarchaeological Analysis of Burials from Chayhuac Walled Complex in Chan Chan Site, Peru*. London, Ontario: Western University, 2017.

Reference: Donnan, Christopher B., and Carol J. Mackey. *Ancient Burial Patterns of the Moche Valley, Peru*. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 1978.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Castillo Luján, Feren. "Tipología Y Seriación De La Cerámica Proveniente Del Cementerio Chimú De Huaca De La Luna, Perú". *Boletín Del Museo Chileno De Arte Precolombino* 23, no. 2 (2018): 27-58. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-68942018000300027>.

Reference: Pollard Rowe, Ann . "Textiles from the Burial Platform of Las Avispas at Chan Chan". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies* 18, no. 1 (1980): 81-148. <https://doi.org/10.1179/naw.1980.18.1.006>.

↳ Personal effects:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, some of the objects (e.g., textiles, headdresses) may have been used by individuals during their lives.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Reference: Donnan, Christopher B., and Carol J. Mackey. *Ancient Burial Patterns of the Moche Valley*, Peru. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 1978.

Reference: Moseley, Michael E., and Kent C. Day, eds.. *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*. Edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. "The Social Basis of Sacred Spaces in the Prehispanic Andes: Ritual Landscapes of the Dead in Chimú and Inka Societies". *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 11, no. 1 (2004): 83-124.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Mackey, Carol . "Chimu Statecraft in the Provinces". In *Andean Civilization: A Tribute to Michael E. Moseley*, edited by Joyce Marcus and Patrick Ryan Williams, 325-50. Los Angeles, CA: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology , 2009.

Reference: Ravines, Rogger, ed.. *Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú*. Edited by Rogger Ravines. Lima: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven

LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– No

Notes: But see burials of llamas in commoners' households in Chan Chan (Topic 1982).

Reference: Topic, John R.. "Lower-class Social and Economic Organization at Chan Chan". In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 145-76. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

↳ Other formal burial type:
– Yes [specify]: See Royal tombs described in General Variables - Architecture, Geography

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Yes

Notes: The Chimu' Staff God, which was depicted on all types of media (pots, clay friezes, metal objects, textiles), may have been the supreme Chimu' deity. However, it is not clear if it was considered a creator god. This anthropomorphic figure holding staffs, symbol of power, was not new to Andean cosmology and it is featured in the iconography of other cultures (e.g., Chavin, Tiwanaku). This deity is front-facing and wears a tunic and a headdress. Unlike during the Early Horizon Chavin depictions, the Chimu' Staff God does not have feline traits (i.e., fangs). This possibly masculine deity is usually associated with animals representing the upper world (birds), the world of the living beings (lizards), and the underworld (snakes, marine beings).

Reference: Mackey, Carol J.. "Los Dioses Que Perdieron Los Colmillos". In *Los Dioses Del Antiguo*

Perú, edited by Krzysztof Makowski, Vol. 2. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito del Perú, 2002.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

Notes: But the king/emperor may have had a special connection to the moon

Reference: Valladares Huamanchumo, Percy. *Historias Del Abuelo*. Lima, Peru: Ediciones Rafael Valdez E. I. R. L., 2021.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, human and animal sacrifices and offerings of Spondylus shells (considered the food of the gods) might have been dedicated to this and other deities

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. "The Thorny Oyster and the Origins of Empire: Implications of Recently Uncovered Spondylus Imagery from Chan Chan, Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 7, no. 4 (1996): 313-40. <https://doi.org/10.2307/972262>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

Reference: Glowacki, Mary. "Food of the Gods or Mere Mortals? Hallucinogenic Spondylus and Its Interpretive Implications for Early Andean Society". *Antiquity* 79, no. 304 (2005): 257-68. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00114061>.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though it is not clear, it is possible that priestly figures communicated with this and other deities

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: As in several other Central Andean cultures, ancestors (mallquis/munaos) were considered important also by the Chimú people. Offerings may have been placed where ancestors were buried and ceremonies in their honor may have been carried out. As mentioned by Uceda and the wooden architectural model found at Huacas de Moche, mummies of ancestors played an important role in ceremonies that may have involved members of the Chimú elites. In addition, places that featured older settlements were likely considered sacred and thus became loci of human sacrifices and burial places of ancestral figures.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Rituales Funerarios De Los Reyes En Una Maqueta Chimú". In *Señores De Los Reinos De La Luna*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski. Lima, Peru: Banco de Crédito - BCP, 2008.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Culto a Los Muertos Y a Los Ancestros: Escenas in Miniatura Y Una Maqueta En La Epoca Chimú". *Arkinka* 49 (1999): 72-83.

Reference: Castillo Luján, Feren. "Descifrando Un Culto a Los Ancestros". *Revista Arqueopáticos* 2, no. 3 (2013): 13-39.

Reference: Ravines, Rogger. "Religion Y Culto a Los Muertos". In *Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú*, edited by Rogger Ravines, 211-16. Lima, Peru: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: Castillo Luján, Feren. "El Chimú Temprano De Huaca De La Luna". In *Actas De La Primera Mesa Redonda De Trujillo. Nuevas Perspectivas En La Arqueología De Los Valles De Virú, Moche Y Chicama*, 232-69. Trujillo, Peru: Fondo Editorial Universitario. Universidad Nacional de Trujillo, 2019.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: As shown by the wooden model found at Huacas de Moche, ancestors may have been shown to small groups of people in enclosed spaces.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Rituales Funerarios De Los Reyes En Una Maqueta Chimú". In *Señores De Los Reinos De La Luna*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski. Lima, Peru: Banco de Crédito - BCP, 2008.

Reference: Uceda, Santiago. "Culto a Los Muertos Y a Los Ancestros: Escenas in Miniatura Y Una Maqueta En La Epoca Chimú". *Arkinka* 49 (1999): 72-83.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As shown by the wooden model found at Huacas de Moche, ancestors may have

been shown to small groups of people in enclosed spaces, but people were likely not allowed to touch them (except for priests).

Reference: Ravines, Rogger. "Religion Y Culto a Los Muertos". In *Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú*, edited by Rogger Ravines, 211-16. Lima, Peru: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Notes: Offerings were made and ceremonies carried out in honor of ancestral figures in the hope that they could have a positive impact on human lives.

Reference: Ravines, Rogger. "Religion Y Culto a Los Muertos". In *Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú*, edited by Rogger Ravines, 211-16. Lima, Peru: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, offerings were made to them.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in other fields of this section, offerings were made and ceremonies carried out in honor of ancestral figures in the hope that they could have a positive impact on human lives. Priests may have had a key role in putting in contact humans and their ancestors.

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination processes:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through specialists:
– No
Notes: Bu they may have played an important role in this

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: In addition to the supreme Staff God, other non-human (yet anthropomorphic) deities were worshipped. The Plumed Headdress Deity, which shares many characteristics with the Staff God. However, this possibly male deity has a different headdress, which features two or more plumes that fall to either side of his cap. This deity may represent another facet of the Staff God, possibly connected to human sacrifices. In fact, this deity usually holds sacrificial knives rather than staffs. It usually appears on ceramics. The Chimú Goddess (a female anthropomorphic being) is usually molded on blackware pots and is depicted while riding a boat. This deity is usually associated with sea motifs (sea birds, Spondylus shells, fish, waves) and moon-like motifs. This deity was thus likely related to the Moon and the Sea. As argued by the chronicler Antonio de la Calancha (1638: 552-553), people living along the North Coast of Peru worshipped the Moon (called Si) and the Sea (called Ni) and they made offering to them. The Moon Animal, which was featured also on objects produced by previous Andean cultures

(e.g., Recuay, Viru') may have also been connected to the Moon and the Sea. This fanged feline-like animal wears a crescent shaped headdress like the Staff God, and is sometimes anthropomorphized. In some cases its tail ends with a fish. Mackey (2002) argues that some animals may have been considered minor deities, namely monkeys and sea creatures. Monkeys, which lived on trees, may have been associated with the sun and the sky. Sea creatures like mantas and Spondylus shells may have been connected to the sea and the underworld.

Reference: Calancha, Antonio de la . *Coronica Moralizada Del Orden De San Agustín En El Perú*. Barcelona, Spain: Pedro Lacavalleria, 1638.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: Mackey, Carol J.. "Los Dioses Que Perdieron Los Colmillos". In *Los Dioses Del Antiguo Perú*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski, Vol. 2. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito del Perú, 2002.

Reference: Ravines, Rogger. "Religion Y Culto a Los Muertos". In *Chan Chan: Metrópoli Chimú*, edited by Rogger Ravines, 211-16. Lima, Peru: Instituto de Estudios Peruanos, 1980.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Offerings were made and ceremonies (including human and animal sacrifices) carried out in honor of these deities in the hope that they could have a positive impact on human lives.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Offerings were made and ceremonies (including human and animal sacrifices) carried out in honor of these deities in the hope that they could have a positive impact on human lives. priestly figures may have mediated between gods and humans.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, offerings (e.g., Spondylus shells) and human sacrifices suggests that deities possessed hunger.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

Reference: Pillsbury, Joanne. "The Thorny Oyster and the Origins of Empire: Implications of Recently Uncovered Spondylus Imagery from Chan Chan, Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 7, no. 4 (1996): 313-40. <https://doi.org/10.2307/972262>.

Reference: Glowacki, Mary. "Food of the Gods or Mere Mortals? Hallucinogenic Spondylus and Its Interpretive Implications for Early Andean Society". *Antiquity* 79, no. 304 (2005): 257-68. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00114061>.

Reference: Cutright, Robyn E. . "Household Ofrendas and Community Feasts: Ritual at a Late Intermediate Period Village in the Jequetepeque Valley, Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies* 33, no. 1 (2013): 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1179/0077629713Z.0000000001>.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, the Chimu' rulers may have had a divine nature

Reference: Valladares Huamanchumo, Percy. *Historias Del Abuelo*. Lima, Peru: Ediciones Rafael Valdez E. I. R. L., 2021.

Reference: Mackey, Carol J.. "Los Dioses Que Perdieron Los Colmillos". In *Los Dioses Del Antiguo Perú*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski, Vol. 2. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito del Perú, 2002.

Reference: Kolata, Alan L. . "The Urban Concept of Chan Chan". In *The Northern Dynasties: Kingship and Statecraft in Chimor*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Alana Cordy-Collins, 107-

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Possibly, with the Staff God at the top of the hierarchy

Reference: Mackey, Carol J.. "Los Dioses Que Perdieron Los Colmillos". In *Los Dioses Del Antiguo Perú*, edited by Krzysztof Makowski, Vol. 2. Lima, Peru: Banco de Credito del Perú, 2002.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: See previous section

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Monogamy (males):

– Field doesn't know

Monogamy (females):

– Field doesn't know

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: According to Rowe (1948: 51), people abstained from sexual intercourse during famine.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: According to Rowe (1948: 51), people abstained from sexual intercourse during famine.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: According to Rowe (1948: 51), people and animals fasted during famine.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: Calancha, Antonio de la . *Coronica Moralizada Del Orden De San Agustín En El Perú*.
Barcelona, Spain: Pedro Lacavalleria, 1638.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: According to Rowe (1948: 51), people abstained from eating salt and chili peppers during famine.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Evidence of Chimu' sacrifices have been found in several river valleys of the Peruvian North Coast. For instance, sacrificed young adult females were found at the burial platform Las Avispas in Chan Chan (Moche Valley), and these individuals may have been wives/concubines of rulers/members of the ruling class. Adult males and females accompanied subadults in the sacrificial events carried out at Huancaquito and Pampa La Cruz in the Moche Valley, and at Chornancap Norte in the Lambayeque Valley. At Pacatnamu' in the Jequetepeque Valley male warriors were killed, in an unusual sacrificial event recalling Moche sacrifices. Male individuals were executed at Punta Lobos in the Huarney Valley. Individuals were mainly killed cutting through the sternum in order to remove the heart. Adult individuals were mainly local individuals (but see possible foreigners/highlanders at Punta Lobos and Pacatnamu'). Sacrificed adults were usually high-status individuals. Except for the warriors at Pacatnamu' and the male individuals executed at Punta Lobos, sacrificed adults were usually carefully buried. Chimu' sacrifices may have been connected to fertility rituals and/or linked to strong El Niño events. Mass human and animal sacrifices may have been carried out to appease gods and stop heavy

rain. However, sacrifices may have been part of a political and ideological strategy carried out by Chimu' rulers in order to keep and reinforce their power during difficult times (see Prieto and Verano 2023).

Reference: Pozorski, Thomas. "The Las Avispas Burial Platform at Chan Chan, Peru". *Annals of Carnegie Museum* 48 (1979).

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Verano, John W., and Marla J. Toyne. "Estudio Bioantropologico De Los Restos Humanos Del Sector II, Punta Lobos, Valle De Huarmey". *Andes* 8 (2011): 449-74.

Reference: Verano, John W., and Sara S. Phillips. "The Killing of Captives on the North Coast of Peru in Pre-hispanic Times". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Haagen D. Klaus and Marla J. Toyne, 244-65. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, and John W. Verano. "From Brave Warriors to Innocent Children: Understanding the Foundations of Ritual Violence in the Moche Valley, North Coast of Peru, A.D. 200-1450". In *Human Sacrifice and Value: Revisiting the Limits of Sacred Violence from an Anthropological and Archaeological Perspective*, edited by Matthew J. Walsh, Sean O'Neill, Marianne Moen, Svein H. Gullbekk, and Eva-Johanna Marie Lafuente Nilsson, 219-57. London: Routledge, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003242475-11>.

↳ Foreign, slaves:

– Yes

Reference: Verano, John W., and Marla J. Toyne. "Estudio Bioantropologico De Los Restos Humanos Del Sector II, Punta Lobos, Valle De Huarmey". *Andes* 8 (2011): 449-74.

Reference: Verano, John W., and Sara S. Phillips. "The Killing of Captives on the North Coast of Peru in Pre-hispanic Times". In *Ritual Violence in the Ancient Andes: Reconstructing Sacrifice on the North Coast of Peru*, edited by Haagen D. Klaus and Marla J. Toyne, 244-65. Austin, TX: University of Texas Press, 2016.

↳ Commoners:

– No

↳ Elites:

– Yes

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Pozorski, Thomas. "The Las Avispas Burial Platform at Chan Chan, Peru". *Annals of Carnegie Museum* 48 (1979).

↳ Other:
– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Yes

Notes: Evidence of Chimú sacrifices of young individuals have been found in several river valleys of the Peruvian North Coast. For instance, young individuals were sacrificed at Chornancap Norte in the Lambayeque Valley, at Huanchaquito and Pampa La Cruz in the Moche Valley, and at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley. Individuals were mainly killed cutting through the sternum in order to remove the heart. Young individuals were mainly local individuals (possible foreigners/highlanders at Huaca Santa Clara, Huanchaquito and Pampa La Cruz). Sacrificed adults were usually high-status individuals. Chimú sacrificed children were usually carefully buried along with grave goods (e.g., decorated textiles, wooden and metal objects, feathers and headdresses). Several times, children were sacrificed along with young camelids. Both children and camelids were in good health when they were sacrificed. Chimú sacrifices may have been connected to fertility rituals and/or linked to strong El Niño events. Mass human and animal sacrifices may have been carried out to appease gods and stop heavy rain. However, sacrifices may have been part of a political and ideological strategy carried out by Chimú rulers in order to keep and reinforce their power during difficult times (see Prieto and Verano 2023).

Reference: Campaña León, Víctor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, and John W. Verano. "From Brave Warriors to Innocent Children: Understanding the Foundations of Ritual Violence in the Moche Valley, North Coast of Peru, A.D. 200-1450". In *Human Sacrifice and Value: Revisiting the Limits of Sacred Violence from an Anthropological and Archaeological Perspective*, edited by Matthew J. Walsh, Sean O'Neill, Marianne Moen, Svein H. Gullbekk, and Eva-Johanna Marie Lafuente Nilsson, 219-57. London: Routledge, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003242475-11>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François, and Flannery Surette. "Un Fardo Funerario Procedente De Huaca

Santa Clara, Valle De Virú (ca. 1150 A. D.)". *Bulletin De L'institut Français D'études Andines* 40, no. 2 (2011): 289–305. <https://doi.org/10.4000/bifea.1408>.

Reference: Hyland, Corrie, Jean-François Millaire, and Paul Szpak. "Migration and Maize in the Virú Valley: Understanding Life Histories Through Multi-tissue Carbon, Nitrogen, Sulfur, and Strontium Isotope Analyses". *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 176, no. 1 (September 2021): 21–35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24271>.

Reference: Millaire, Jean-François. "The Sacred Character of Ruins on the Peruvian North Coast". In *Living with the Dead in the Andes*, edited by Izumi Shimada and James L. Fitzsimmons, 50–75. Tucson, AZ: The University of Arizona Press, 2015.

Reference: Dufour, Elise, Nicolas Goepfert, Manon Le Neün, Gabriel Prieto, and John W. Verano. "Life History and Origin of the Camelids Provisioning a Mass Killing Sacrifice During the Chimú Period: Insight from Stable Isotopes". *Environmental Archaeology. Special Issue: Past Andean Pastoralism: A Reconsidered Diversity*. 25, no. 3 (2020): 310–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14614103.2018.1498165>.

Reference: Goepfert, Nicolas, Elise Dufour, Gabriel Prieto, and John W. Verano. "Herds for the Gods? Selection Criteria and Herd Management at the Mass Sacrifice Site of Huanchaquito-las Llamas During the Chimú Period, Northern Coast of Peru". *Environmental Archaeology. Special Issue: Past Andean Pastoralism: A Reconsidered Diversity*. 25, no. 3 (2020): 296–309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14614103.2018.1541956>.

Reference: Cagnato, Clarissa, Michelle Elliott, Gabriel Prieto, John W. Verano, and Elise Dufour. "Eat and Die: The Last Meal of Sacrificed Chimú Camelids at Huanchaquito-las Llamas, Peru, as Revealed by Starch Grain Analysis". *Latin American Antiquity* 32, no. 3 (2021): 595–611. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2021.19>.

Foreign, slaves:

– Yes

Notes: Foreign children were likely sacrificed during Chimu' rituals. At Pampa La Cruz and Huanchaquito, annular cranial modifications suggest about 15% of the individuals may have come from highland communities. In the sacrificial event carried out at Huaca Santa Clara in the Viru' Valley, isotopic analyses and observations made on cranial modifications suggest that children from the highlands and the intermediate zones between coast and Andes were sacrificed.

Reference: Hyland, Corrie, Jean-François Millaire, and Paul Szpak. "Migration and Maize in the Virú Valley: Understanding Life Histories Through Multi-tissue Carbon, Nitrogen, Sulfur, and Strontium Isotope Analyses". *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 176, no. 1 (September 2021): 21–35. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24271>.

Reference: Campaña León, Victor, and Gabriel Prieto. *Excavando Pampa La Cruz: Proyecto De Rescate Arqueológico Las Lomas De Huanchaco 2017-2018*. Lima, Peru: Rafael Valdez Ediciones, 2022.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1–86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the

Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, and John W. Verano. "From Brave Warriors to Innocent Children: Understanding the Foundations of Ritual Violence in the Moche Valley, North Coast of Peru, A.D. 200-1450". In *Human Sacrifice and Value: Revisiting the Limits of Sacred Violence from an Anthropological and Archaeological Perspective*, edited by Matthew J. Walsh, Sean O'Neill, Marianne Moen, Svein H. Gullbekk, and Eva-Johanna Marie Lafuente Nilsson, 219-57. London: Routledge, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003242475-11>.

↳ Commoners:

– No

↳ Elites:

– Yes

Notes: The careful treatment of the bodies and the good health of the individuals suggest that they were from high status families.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John W. Verano, Nicolas Goepfert, Douglas Kennett, Jeffrey Quilter, Steven LeBlanc, Lars Fehren-Schmitz, et al.. "A Mass Sacrifice of Children and Camelids at the Huanchaquito-las Llamas Site, Moche Valley, Peru". *Plosone* 14, no. 3 (2019): e0211691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0211691>.

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: The excavation of commoners' households and workshops in Chan Chan led to the discovery of a pot containing objects related to metalworking and *Spondylus* shells (see Topic 1982:158). Evidence from a provincial village in the Jequetepeque Valley shows that maize, *Spondylus* shells, human hair, and textiles were used as offering in residential spaces.

Reference: Cutright, Robyn E. . "Household Ofrendas and Community Feasts: Ritual at a Late Intermediate Period Village in the Jequetepeque Valley, Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies* 33, no. 1 (2013): 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1179/0077629713Z.0000000001>.

Reference: Topic, John R.. "Lower-class Social and Economic Organization at Chan Chan". In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 145-76. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: The large plazas featured in Chan Chan and in other large provincial centers like Manchán and Farfan were probably places where large-scale feasts and dances were performed. It should be noted that access to royal compounds or *ciudadelas* was highly restricted and their massive walls reinforced the separations between social classes. Thus, it can be argued that only specific shares of the populations participated in these ceremonies, which may have also involved the display of mummy bundles/ancestors.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. "The Social Basis of Sacred Spaces in the Prehispanic Andes: Ritual Landscapes of the Dead in Chimú and Inka Societies". *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 11, no. 1 (2004): 83-124.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. "The Archaeology of Plazas and the Proxemics of Ritual: Three Andean

Traditions". *American Anthropologist* 98, no. 4 (1996): 789–802.
<https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1996.98.4.02a00090>.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D.. *Architecture and Power in the Ancient Andes the Archaeology of Public Buildings*. Cambridge University Press, 1996. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511521201>.

Reference: Mackey, Carol . "Chimu Statecraft in the Provinces". In *Andean Civilization: A Tribute to Michael E. Moseley*, edited by Joyce Marcus and Patrick Ryan Williams, 325–50. Los Angeles, CA: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology , 2009.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not clear if intoxicants were used, but it is possible that maize beer (chicha) was consumed during ceremonies. In addition, Spondylus meat may have been used as an hallucinogen (Glowacki 2005).

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: Glowacki, Mary. "Food of the Gods or Mere Mortals? Hallucinogenic Spondylus and Its Interpretive Implications for Early Andean Society". *Antiquity* 79, no. 304 (2005): 257–68.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00114061>.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Cranial modifications were found in Chimu' burials, but they were likely not connected to religious affiliation

Reference: Prieto, Gabriel, John Verano, Ann Pollard Rowe, Feren Castillo, Luis Flores, Julio Asencio, Alan Chachapoyas, et al.. "Pampa La Cruz: A New Mass Sacrificial Burial Ground During the Chimú Occupation in Huanchaco, North Coast of Peru". *Ñawpa Pacha: Journal of the Institute of Andean Studies*, 2023, 1-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00776297.2023.2221481>.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of storage rooms both in Chan Chan and in administrative centers located in the Moche and in other valleys suggested the Chimu' empire stored perishable (i.e., food) and non perishable (e.g., metals, textiles) goods. Perishable goods might have also been stored to support the population in case of famine caused by meteorological events such as El Niño.

Reference: Correa-Trigoso, Denis E.. "Los Depósitos Y Las Áreas De Almacenamiento En La Urbe Chimú: Chan Chan, Trujillo, Perú". *SPAL - Revista De Prehistoria Y Arqueología* 30.1 (2021): 310-33. <https://doi.org/10.12795/spal.2021.i30.12>.

Reference: Keatinge, Richard W., and Kent C. Day. "Socio-economic Organization of the Moche Valley, Peru, During the Chimu Occupation of Chan Chan". *Journal of Anthropological Research* 29, no. 4 (1973): 275-95.

Reference: Keatinge, Richard W., and Geoffrey W. Conrad. "Imperialist Expansion in Peruvian Prehistory: Chimu Administration of a Conquered Territory". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 10, no. 3 (1983): 255–83. <https://doi.org/10.2307/529543>.

Reference: Day, Kent C.. "Ciudadelas: Their Form and Function". In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 55–65. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Chimu' empire bureaucratic structure.

Reference: Mackey, Carol . "Chimu Statecraft in the Provinces". In *Andean Civilization: A Tribute to*

Michael E. Moseley, edited by Joyce Marcus and Patrick Ryan Williams, 325–50. Los Angeles, CA: Cotsen Institute of Archaeology, 2009.

Reference: Fogel, Heidy, Michael E. Moseley, and Alana Cordy-Collins. “The Northern Dynasties: Kingship and Statecraft in Chimor” 19, no. 2 (1992). <https://doi.org/10.2307/529993>.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. “The Chimú Empire”. In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Keatinge, Richard W., and Geoffrey W. Conrad. “Imperialist Expansion in Peruvian Prehistory: Chimu Administration of a Conquered Territory”. *Journal of Field Archaeology* 10, no. 3 (1983): 255–83. <https://doi.org/10.2307/529543>.

Reference: Moseley, Michael E., and Kent C. Day, eds.. *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*. Edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the Welfare section, several Chimu' administrative sites feature storerooms. Some of these storerooms may have been filled with staple foods.

Reference: Correa-Trigoso, Denis E.. “Los Depósitos Y Las Áreas De Almacenamiento En La Urbe Chimú: Chan Chan, Trujillo, Perú”. *SPAL - Revista De Prehistoria Y Arqueología* 30.1 (2021): 310–33. <https://doi.org/10.12795/spal.2021.i30.12>.

Reference: Day, Kent C.. “Ciudadelas: Their Form and Function”. In *Chan Chan: Andean Desert City*, edited by Michael E. Moseley and Kent C. Day, 55–65. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press, 1982.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Chimu' empire likely sponsored the construction of complex irrigation networks to bring water to large swaths of the arid Peruvian North Coast. These public works may have been built and maintained through a labor tax system. In some cases, the presence of Chimu' rural administrative centers in the vicinity of canals suggests a strong control over land, water, and labor by the empire. However, small canals were likely managed by local communities and their leaders.

Reference: Ortloff, Charles R., and Michael E. Moseley. "Climate, Agricultural Strategies, and Sustainability in the Precolumbian Andes". *Andean Past* 9 (2009): 277-304.

Reference: Ortloff, Charles R.. "Canal Builders of Pre-inca Peru". *Scientific American* 259, no. 6 (1988): 100-107.

Reference: Ortloff, Charles R., Robert A. Feldman, and Michael E. Moseley. "Hydraulic Engineering and Historical Aspects of the Pre-columbian Intravalley Canal Systems of the Moche Valley, Peru". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 12, no. 1 (1985): 77-98. <https://doi.org/10.2307/529376>.

Reference: Netherly, Patricia J.. "The Management of Late Andean Irrigation Systems on the North Coast of Peru". *American Antiquity* 49, no. 2 (1984). <https://doi.org/10.2307/280017>.

Reference: Hayashida, Frances. "The Pampa De Chaparrí: Water, Land, and Politics on the North Coast of Peru". *Latin American Antiquity* 17, no. 3 (2006): 243-63. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1045663500013900>.

Reference: Keatinge, Richard W., and Kent C. Day. "Socio-economic Organization of the Moche Valley, Peru, During the Chimú Occupation of Chan Chan". *Journal of Anthropological Research* 29, no. 4 (1973): 275-95.

Reference: Keatinge, Richard W.. "Chimú Rural Administrative Centres in the Moche Valley, Peru". *World Archaeology* 6, no. 1 (1974): 66-82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00438243.1974.9979589>.

Reference: Pozorski, Thomas, and Shelia Pozorski. "Prehistoric Chimú Irrigation Strategies on the Peruvian North Coast". In *Kay Pacha: Cultivating Earth and Water in the Andes*, edited by Penelope Dransart, 171-85. BAR International Series 1478. Oxford, UK: BAR Publishing, 2006.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The empire sponsored the construction of roads that connected the lands (especially the main administrative centers) that were conquered over the centuries.

Reference: Moore, Jerry D., and Carol J. Mackey. "The Chimú Empire". In *The Handbook of South American Archaeology*, edited by Helaine Silverman and William H. Isbell. New York: Springer, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79407-5>.

Reference: Keatinge, Richard W., and Geoffrey W. Conrad. "Imperialist Expansion in Peruvian Prehistory: Chimú Administration of a Conquered Territory". *Journal of Field Archaeology* 10, no. 3 (1983): 255-83. <https://doi.org/10.2307/529543>.

Reference: Beck, Colleen M.. *Ancient Roads on the North Coast of Peru*. Berkeley, CA: University of California, 1979.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes were likely paid by labor, using a system that recalls the Inka mit'a system. Labor was used to carry out various activities, such as build public works (e.g., irrigation canals), construct monuments, create a variety of objects (e.g., pots, textiles, metal ornaments, etc...) and farm arable land. Goods produced by craftsmen and farmers were then stored in the storerooms featured in several administrative centers.

Reference: Moseley, Michael E. "Prehistoric Principles of Labor Organization in the Moche Valley, Peru". *American Antiquity* 40, no. 2 (1975): 191-96. <https://doi.org/10.2307/279614>.

Reference: D'Altroy, Terence N.. *The Incas*. 2nd ed.. Wiley Blackwell, 2014.

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Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents to the cult interacted/were likely part of the Chimu' imperial army.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: However, John Rowe (1948: 48) argues that the Chimu' empire had a legal system with brutal punishments.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned above, John Rowe (1948: 48) argues that the Chimu' empire had a legal system with brutal punishments. For example, people that disrespected shrines were buried alive.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: John Rowe (1948: 48) argues that the Chimu' empire had a legal system with brutal punishments. For example, people that disrespected shrines were buried alive.

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s)

other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherent to the Chimu' religion were likely part of the imperial army.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though it is not clear if there was a formal calendar, the chronicler Antonio de la Calancha (1638, p. 588) tells us that for people living on the North Coast of Peru the heliacal rising (early June) of the Pleiades (Fur in Quingnam language) marked the beginning of the year. The Pleiades were also considered patrons of crops and their periodicities defined the fishing seasons of people living on the Peruvian North Coast (Rowe 1948; Urton 1982).

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

Reference: Calancha, Antonio de la . *Coronica Moralizada Del Orden De San Agustín En El Perú*. Barcelona, Spain: Pedro Lacavalleria, 1638.

Reference: Urton, Gary. "Astronomy and Calendrics on the Coast of Peru", *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 385, *Ethnoastronomy and Archaeoastronomy in the American Tropics* (1982).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See previous answer

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Reference: Rowe, John H. . "The Kingdom of Chimor", *Acta Americana*, 6 (1948).

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